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Deliverable D4.2

Semantic Communications under Timing Constraints: First results

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Abstract

6G-GOALS project challenges the conventional content-agnostic transmission approach, questioning its relevance for AI processes. Instead of assuming that receivers always benefit from all transmitted data, the 6G-GOALS framework aims to emphasize that information is valuable only when it has practical, exploitable significance for the receiver, which includes its timely reception. In this context, time emerges as a critical dimension that dictates the value and relevance of transmitted information: not only must the conveyed information be meaningful, but it must also arrive within a temporal window where it can influence decisions or actions. Late information, even if accurate, may be useless for real-time control or inference, while overly aggressive timing wastes bandwidth and energy. Consequently, intelligent decision-making is inherently tied to both the urgency and utility of information. Recognizing this, Task 4.2 “Semantic communications under timing constraints” is dedicated to developing a comprehensive and systematic characterization and analysis of time in general sensing-computation-communication systems, such as those envisioned in 6G-GOALS. This first deliverable, D4.2, develops the theoretical underpinnings for such systems, with the focus on the 6G-GOALS use cases, and including dynamic temporal representations, the use of advanced AI methods like foundation models and human-in-the-loop reinforcement learning, and a timing framework based on stochastic network calculus and saddle point approximations. These initial insights, together with the reasoning and causal representations of D4.1 and D4.3, set the basis for future work on resource-aware SemCom and goal-oriented optimization and protocol design of WP5.

Keywords

Semantic Communications, goal-oriented, human-in-the-loop, semantic error correction, foundation model, timing framework, networked cyber-physical systems, stochastic network calculus, joint optimization, control, push/pull based communications, closed-loop

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
6G	6th Generation
ACK	ACKnowledgement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AoI	Age of Information
AoL	Age of Loop
AP	Access Point
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BFF	Bloom Filtering Factor
BS	Base Station
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CGC	Closed-loop Goal-oriented Communications
CP	Control Plane
CSI	Channel State Information
CU	Centralized Unit
CSMA	Carrier Sense Multiple Access
DL	Deep Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DQN	Deep Q-Network
DRX	Discontinuous Reception
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
FL	Federated Learning
FM	Foundation Model
GO	Goal Oriented
HITL	Human-in-the-Loop
IoT	Internet of Things
ITS	Intelligent Transportation Systems
JSCC	Joint Source and Channel Coding
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LL	Lossless
LLM	Large Language Model
MAC	Medium Access Control
MDN	Mixture Density Network
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
MGF	Moment Generating Function
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NMSE	Normalised Mean Squared Error
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access
O-RAN	Open RAN
OT	Optimal Transport
PAPR	Peak-to-Average Power Ratio
PEFT	Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning
PDF	Probability Density Function
PDCCH	Physical Downlink Control Channel
PMF	Probability Mass Function
POMDP	Partially Observable Markov Decision Process
PRB	Physical Resource Block

PSD	Power Spectral Density
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
RA	Remote Agent
RB	Resource Block
QI	Query Interval
RIC	Radio Access Network Intelligent Controller
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RT	Real Time
RU	Radio Unit
RX	Receiver
RR	Relative Representation
SPA	Saddle Point Approximation
SemCom	Semantic Communication
TTI	Time Transmission Interval
TX	Transmitter
UE	User Equipment
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
Vol	Value of Information
WNCS	Wireless Network Control System
WuR	Wake-up Radio
WuS	Wake-up Signal

1 Introduction

The 6G-GOALS framework envisions a fundamental shift from traditional data-centric communication towards a goal-oriented (GO) and semantic communication (SemCom) paradigm [CDS+24]. This approach integrates data acquisition, computation, communication, control, and intelligence into a unified architectural vision. To achieve this objective, the 6G-GOALS project challenges the conventional content-agnostic transmission approach, questioning its relevance for Artificial Intelligence (AI) processes. Instead of assuming that receivers always benefit from all transmitted data, the 6G-GOALS framework aims to emphasize that information is valuable only when it has practical, exploitable significance for the receiver, which includes its timely reception.

In this setting, **time is** not merely a transmission parameter but **a fundamental dimension that dictates both the value and relevance of transmitted information**. For information to be actionable, it must be not only semantically relevant but also delivered within a time frame in which it can shape decisions or drive actions. Information that arrives too late, however accurate, may fail to serve its purpose in real-time inference or control. Conversely, transmitting data too early or too often can lead to inefficient use of bandwidth and energy. Therefore, the utility of information is inseparable from its timeliness, and intelligent decision-making must account for both temporal urgency and contextual relevance. Recognizing this, Task 4.2 “Semantic communications under timing constraints” is dedicated to developing a comprehensive and systematic characterization and analysis of time in general sensing-computation-communication systems, such as those envisioned in 6G-GOALS.

For this, the first deliverable of Task 4.2 lays the foundation of SemCom and GO in systems with time constraints by presenting the theoretical frameworks that allow the analysis of these systems. This includes the development of dynamic relative representations for time-sensitive SemCom, the use of advanced AI tools such as Foundation Models and Human-in-the-Loop Reinforcement Learning for GO communications. It also introduces a timing framework based on stochastic network calculus and saddle point approximations for networked cyber-physical systems. The deep understanding of how timing dynamics interact is essential to guide subsequent resource optimizations strategies in both GO and SemCom designs, which is the objective of this task.

1.1 Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the main theoretical frameworks leveraged for time-constrained optimizations and learning, including relative representations, time-constrained reinforcement learning and foundation models. Then, Section 3 introduces a timing framework and associated methods to analyse general SemCom and GO systems, providing a hierarchy of tools for the design and evaluation of time-critical cyber-physical systems. Later, Section 4 presents several goal-oriented optimization strategies tailored for sensing-computation-communication systems across different application domains, including IoT, Digital Twin, and V2X. In each case, the interplay between energy consumption, time, and task completion introduces complex trade-offs that demand careful and detailed analysis. These trade-offs are highly dependent on system dynamics, task urgency, and resource constraints, highlighting the need and potential of SemCom and GO optimizations. Finally, Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

2 Time-Constrained Optimization and Learning for Semantic Communication

This section presents three complementary theoretical frameworks that address time-constrained optimization and learning for semantic communication. First, we explore *relative representations* (RRs) for dynamically aligning heterogeneous encoders and reducing both computational and communication overhead. We then discuss a *time-constrained reinforcement learning* framework that incorporates user feedback for semantic error correction under strict latency bounds. Finally, we introduce an approach based on *foundation models* (FMs), which leverages parameter-efficient personalization to handle diverse data and tasks in multi-user scenarios without exhaustive retraining. Together, these works illustrate diverse strategies for ensuring robust, adaptable, and time-sensitive semantic communication.

2.1 Dynamic relative representations for time-sensitive semantic communications

Context and motivation

In Semantic Communications (SemCom), the problem of estimating correspondences between two latent spaces is treated as a case of Semantic Channel Equalization that aims to equalize the semantic discrepancies between a transmitter and a receiver within a communication system. For instance, in [SS23], the authors propose an algorithm that relies on a codebook of low-complexity linear transformations to map between the atoms (i.e., regions of shared semantic meaning) in the transmitter and receiver latent spaces, governed by a suitable selection policy. In [HSS24], this challenge is addressed by defining the atoms in a self-supervised manner, which improves overall performance. Nonetheless, the process still relies on labelled data for atom identification, and the transformation selection policy requires precise atom estimation. In [MMF+22], the authors introduce the relative representations (RRs) framework to establish a common semantic representation between distinct, independently trained DNN-based encoding functions in a zero-shot manner, thereby eliminating the need to retrain the models. This approach enables, under certain assumptions, the alignment of latent spaces derived from different encoding functions when they share the same underlying data semantics. The effectiveness of RRs for unifying representations has been demonstrated for both text and image data [MMF+22] as well as for reinforcement learning problems [RMM+24]. Multiple metrics for computing the similarity score have also been explored [CMF+23], and their generalization capabilities have been showcased [NFM+23]. The rationale of RR is explained in the following.

Consider an encoding function, $E: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, trained on the dataset X , that maps an input signal to a lower-dimensional latent space, i.e., its absolute space, $e_x := E(x) \in \mathbb{R}^d$. A subset of X is defined as the anchor set, $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_{|A|}\}$. A generic similarity function, $d: \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, is used to compute the similarity between any two absolute representations. Therefore, the relative representation for a generic encoding function is defined as [MMF+22]:

$$\mathbf{r}_x(E, A) = [d(e_x, e_{a_1}), \dots, d(e_x, e_{a_{|A|}})].$$

Then, a *relative decoder* function,

$$D_A: \mathbb{R}^{|A|} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{|T|}$$

is trained to perform a downstream task T , enabling it to interpret the relationships represented in the relative representation and accurately extract meaning. Consequentially, this approach unifies semantically equivalent latent spaces and allows dynamic semantic compression based on the number of anchors used. A more complete analysis of the RR in SemCom is provided in [6G-GOALS-D4.1], and the scenario is depicted in Figure 2-1. In this contribution, we focus on the novel ideas of [FBC+24] and the dynamic optimization.

Figure 2-1 System Model. The edge device (TX) encodes data according to the optimal encoder-anchor set pair. The RX is equipped with relative decoders trained on shared anchor sets to interpret the transmitted relative representations.

Relative (rather than absolute) embeddings are particularly useful in AI-native communication systems, where TXs and RXs naturally share semantically meaningful features. By transmitting RRs, a TX can switch among multiple encoders on the fly, while the RX (equipped with relative decoders) still interprets the message without retraining. As shown in [FBC+24], this strategy lightens the deployment overhead on edge devices by shifting most semantic processing to the RX, which only needs to store decoders associated with different anchor sets. Motivated by these advantages, the present work introduces the time dimension and develops a dynamic resource allocation framework that leverages RRs to balance latency, energy efficiency, and accuracy in goal-oriented communications. By adapting in each time slot the number of anchors, the choice of encoder, and relevant communication/computation parameters, we provide simple closed-form solutions, requiring no prior knowledge of channel or computation statistics, to ensure robust semantic alignment and efficiency in time-sensitive wireless environments.

System Model and problem statement

We devise a dynamic allocation of computation (e.g., CPU clock frequency), communication (e.g., data rate), and learning (e.g., number of anchors, encoders) resources for goal-oriented communication involving inference tasks, while promoting a semantic understanding of the transmitted information. We assume to have sets E and A of pre-trained encoders and anchor sets, respectively, available on the TX side. The RX is assumed to know A , and to have a set of relative decoders (one for each anchor set) to guarantee the semantic alignment between the different pre-trained encoders. The relative decoders are assumed to be trained using the RRs generated from an arbitrary encoder, which could belong or not to E . In this setting, context parameters like channel quality, data characteristics, and variations in how devices model information (i.e., the semantic language) can fluctuate. Consequently, the proposed methodology aims to achieve an optimal trade-off between power consumption, latency, and inference accuracy by working on the semantic integrity of the communication. The choice of the encoder and the anchor set directly impacts the achievable compression and the computational demands on the TX: complex models may extract more meaningful information but require higher computational frequencies, consuming more power; similarly, a larger anchor set allows for more nuanced RRs but increases the volume of data that needs to be transmitted.

We assume a simplified RX that incurs negligible decoding delay. Perfect channel state information (CSI) is assumed to be available at the TX. We work with a time-slot-based model, where the system adaptively and dynamically optimizes resource allocation within each time slot. Power consumption: At time t , we focus on the dynamic power consumption originating from

the two main controllable contributors, local computation and transmission. The local computation power is $p_t^c = \kappa f_t^3$, where κ is the switched capacitance and f_t the CPU frequency. Instead, the transmission power is defined as

$$p_t^u = \frac{N_0}{|h_t|^2} \left[\exp\left(\frac{R_t \ln 2}{B}\right) - 1 \right],$$

where N_0 is the noise spectral density, $|h_t|^2$ the channel gain, R_t the data rate, and B the bandwidth. Therefore, the total dynamic power consumption is given by

$$p_t = p_t^u + p_t^c.$$

Latency: The overall latency of each time slot has two main sources of delay: the local processing time and the uplink communication time. Local processing time can be computed as

$$L_t^c = \frac{N_{E_t, A_t}}{f_t},$$

where N_{E_t, A_t} depends on the encoder E_t and anchor set A_t . Instead, the uplink communication time is

$$L_t^u = \frac{n_{A_t, q}}{R_t},$$

where $n_{A_t, q}$ is the number of bits to transmit. The total latency is $L_t = L_t^u + L_t^c$. Learning accuracy: We assume the RX has access to a validation set X^{val} . A task-specific function G_{E_t, A_t} evaluates learning performance based on the encoder E and anchor set A . Specifically, for classification tasks, it can be computed as:

$$G_{E_t, A_t} = \frac{1}{|X^{val}|} \sum_{x, y \in X^{val}} \mathbb{1}(\hat{y}_{E_t, A_t}(x) = y),$$

where $\hat{y}_{E_t, A_t}(x)$ is the prediction using the encoder E_t and the anchor set A_t .

Problem Formulation: We can now formulate the problem of dynamic resource allocation for goal-oriented communication. The aim is to find the optimal policy to allocate, at each t , the uplink data rate R_t , the CPU cycles at devices f_t , the encoder E_t and the anchor set A_t to minimize the long-term average system power consumption (transmission and computation), with constraints on the average inference accuracy and the average latency. The dynamic resource allocation problem can then be cast as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{R_t, f_t, E_t, A_t} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{p_\tau\} \\ & \text{s. t. } (a) \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{\mathbb{1}_{[L_\tau \geq L^{ist}]}\} \leq p^{IST}; \\ & \quad (b) \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{L_\tau\} \leq \bar{L}; \\ & \quad (c) \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbb{E}\{G_\tau\} \geq \bar{G}; \\ & \quad (d) R^{min} \leq R_t \leq R^{max}; \\ & \quad (e) f_t^{min} < f_t \leq f_t^{max}; \\ & \quad (f) E_t \in \mathbf{E}; \\ & \quad (g) A_t \in \mathbf{A}; \end{aligned}$$

Expectations are taken over the relevant random variables in the system, i.e., the channel condition and the available computation frequency at the TX side. G_τ is a short-hand notation for

G_{E_t, A_t} . The constraints of this problem have the following meanings: (a) ensures that the probability for the instantaneous latency to exceed a certain value L^{IST} does not exceed a threshold p^{IST} ; (b) ensures that the mean latency does not exceed a threshold \bar{L} ; (c) ensures that the mean accuracy of the system does not decrease under a certain threshold \bar{G} . Imposing both constraints (a) and (b) is instrumental to better control the statistical distribution of latency. Finally, the constraints in (d)-(g) impose instantaneous bounds (e.g., minimum rates and maximum CPU frequencies) on the resource variables R_t, f_t , and impose that E_t and A_t can take values only from finite sets \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{A} encoders and anchor sets, respectively.

Proposed methodology and solution

We introduce a dynamic algorithmic framework to solve the long-term optimization problem defined in the previous section by recasting it as a stability problem via the tools of stochastic Lyapunov optimization [N10]. By minimizing an upper bound of the drift-plus-penalty and exploiting opportunistic minimization, we reach the following per-slot problem [FBC+24]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{R_t, f_t, E_t, A_t} \quad & (Z_t + Y_t)L_t - Q_t G_t + V \cdot p_t^{tot} \\ \text{s. t.} \quad & (d) R^{min} \leq R_t \leq R^{max}; \\ & (e) f_t^{min} < f_t \leq f_t^{max}; \\ & (f) E_t \in \mathbf{E}; \\ & (g) A_t \in \mathbf{A}; \end{aligned}$$

Here, Z_t, Y_t and Q_t are the values of the virtual queues introduced for the constraints (a), (b), and (c), respectively. Instead, V is a weighting parameter that balances the stabilization of the virtual queues with the minimization of the system's total dynamic power. Now, because of (d)-(e)-(f)-(g), this new problem is a mixed-integer non-linear optimization problem. However, for any given A_t and E_t , the problem becomes convex in R_t and f_t . Therefore, we can derive the optimal uplink rate R_t^* and CPU frequency f_t^* by imposing the KKT's conditions [BV04], obtaining,

$$\begin{aligned} R_t^* &= \left[\frac{2B}{\ln 2} W \left(\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(Z_t + Y_t) n_{A_t} q |h_t|^2 \ln 2}{BV N_0}} \right) \right]_{R^{min}}^{R^{max}}, \\ f_t^* &= \left[\sqrt[4]{\frac{(Z_t + Y_t) N_t}{3V\kappa}} \right]_{f_t^{min}}^{f_t^{max}}. \end{aligned}$$

To select the best encoders and anchor set, the algorithm evaluates the objective function for every possible combination using the optimal communication and computation parameters. This results in $|\mathbf{E}| \times |\mathbf{A}|$ independent evaluations, where $|\mathbf{E}|$ and $|\mathbf{A}|$ are the cardinalities of the encoder and anchor sets.

Results

Our simulation setup employs a set of pre-trained encoders \mathbf{E} and anchor sets \mathbf{A} , as in Figure 2-2. Specifically, pre-trained encoders were derived by removing the final classifier from models originally trained on ImageNet [DDS+09]. The relative decoders were then trained using a frozen *mobilenetv3_large_100* encoder on the CIFAR-10 dataset [KH09]. As a result, performance for *mobilenetv3_large_100* represents the end-to-end benchmark, while the results for the other encoders showcase the effectiveness of zero-shot stitching. In developing the RR design, we followed the approach proposed in [MMF+22]. We employed cosine similarity as the similarity function based on the assumption that the angles between data representations remain consistent across different encoding functions. The anchor sets are generated through a uniform random selection of samples from the training dataset. This methodology balances simplicity in implementation and robustness in performance outcomes. To assess the performance of our

dynamic resource allocation framework, we run the proposed algorithm while varying the constraints on average latency and average accuracy. This allows us to explore the inherent trade-offs between power consumption, latency, and inference accuracy, highlighting our approach’s flexibility.

Figure 2-2 Performance of zero-shot stitching using different pre-trained encoders and varying anchor set sizes on the CIFAR-10 classification task. The dashed line is end-to-end performance.

We optimize, across 5 random seeds, according to the following \bar{L} values [0.03,0.04,0.05,0.06] (s) and \bar{G} values [0.7,0.8,0.9]. The channel considers path loss propagation, the message quantization is set to 32 bits, and the channel bandwidth is 1 MHz. To ensure timely responses, we define a maximum tolerable latency $L^{IST} = \bar{L} + 7.5 \times 10^{-3}$ s with a corresponding probability threshold of $p^{ist} = 0.3$. Then, in Figure 2-3, we illustrate the behaviour of the average power versus the average latency constraints \bar{L} for different accuracy constraints \bar{G} . As we can notice, RRs enable the effective exchange of semantic information for all system configurations; as expected, more stringent accuracy constraints necessitate more computationally expensive choices for a given latency constraint.

Figure 2-3 Long-term average power vs \bar{L} , for different \bar{G} .

Finally, Figure 2-4 illustrates the instantaneous behaviour of latency (top) and accuracy (bottom) for a specific system configuration, i.e., $\bar{L} = 0.04$ s and $\bar{G} = 0.8$, showing the capability of the proposed solution to guarantee the long-term constraints.

Figure 2-4 Latency and accuracy vs t , $\bar{L}=0.04$ s and $\bar{G}=0.8$.

Conclusions

The work in [FBC+24] introduced a novel framework for goal-oriented and SemCom, addressing the challenges posed by semantic mismatches in dynamic environments. Our key contributions lie in using RRs for robust communication across diverse devices and a dynamic resource optimization strategy for goal-oriented tasks. This strategy adapts communication, computation, and learning resources to enable low-latency, energy-efficient inference crucial for edge applications. Numerical results validate the effectiveness of our framework in achieving a favourable trade-off between energy consumption, delay, and inference reliability.

2.2 AI for time-constrained goal-oriented communications

2.2.1 Time-Constrained HITL-RL for Semantic Error Correction

Context and motivation

SemCom represents a fundamental shift from traditional symbol-level transmission to meaning-centric communication, aiming to transmit only the most relevant information necessary to fulfil the communication goal. While this paradigm significantly improves communication efficiency, it introduces new challenges, particularly the problem of semantic errors, discrepancies between intended and received meanings. Previous studies in [6G-GOALS-D4.1] have introduced semantic error detection and correction frameworks using variational autoencoders (VAE), Gaussian Process (GP)-based anomaly detection, and Human-in-the-Loop Reinforcement Learning (HITL-RL). These efforts have been effective in integrating user feedback into the semantic model refinement process, particularly in multi-user broadcasting scenarios [LLA25]. However, these solutions often overlook the critical timing requirements imposed by real-time applications such as vehicular communication, augmented reality, and mission-critical IoT.

This work proposes a novel extension to the HITL-RL framework by incorporating timing constraints into the decision-making loop. The goal is to enable real-time semantic model adaptation while satisfying strict latency requirements in multi-user broadcasting SemCom systems. In broadcasting SemCom systems, a single transmitter serves multiple UEs, each with diverse and potentially time-sensitive requirements. In scenarios where semantic fidelity is user-dependent and latency-sensitive, there arises a need for:

1. Rapid identification of semantic degradation due to factors like channel variation, input feature shifts, or user preference drift.
2. Timely adaptation of the semantic model using a limited time budget.
3. Balancing the trade-off between semantic accuracy improvements and the time cost of reconfiguration.

Traditional HITL-RL frameworks optimize for semantic accuracy and user satisfaction without accounting for the time taken to reconfigure models. In time-critical applications, even a well-performing action may be suboptimal if it exceeds a time deadline. Therefore, timing-aware decision-making becomes essential. The overall system of this timing-constrained HITL-RL for semantic model update is illustrated in Figure 2-5.

Figure 2-5: Illustration of the timing-constrained HITL-RL for semantic model update

System model and problem statement

We formulate the adaptive semantic communication problem under timing constraints as a Time-Constrained Markov Decision Process (CMDP). This CMDP formalism captures the need to jointly optimize semantic performance while respecting bounded decision latency. We define CMDP as a tuple $M = \langle S, A, P, R, C, \gamma, d \rangle$, where:

- S is the state space, representing the system's current semantic status, user conditions, model configuration, environment context, and accumulated elapsed time.
- A represents the action space, including operations like model reconfiguration, fine-tuning, knowledge base (KB) updates, or resource allocation.
- $P(s' | s, a)$ is the state transition probability, defining the dynamics of the system after acting a in state s .
- $R(s, a)$ represents the primary reward function, encoding semantic utility (e.g., communication effectiveness, user satisfaction, or semantic fidelity).
- $C(s, a)$ is the cost function, representing the time duration or latency incurred by executing action a in state s .
- $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ represents the discount factor for future rewards.
- d is the maximum allowable cumulative time (i.e., a timing budget).

The cumulative time cost over a decision trajectory can be represented as: $\tau = (s_0, a_0), (s_1, a_1), \dots$ can be presented as:

$$C(\tau) = \sum_{t=0}^T C(s_t, a_t).$$

The objective is to find a policy $\pi: S \rightarrow A$ that maximizes expected total reward while respecting a hard timing constraint:

$$\max_{\pi} E_{\pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^{tR} (s_t, a_t) \right]$$

$$\text{subject to } E_{\pi} [\sum_{t=0}^T C(s_t, a_t)] \leq d.$$

Alternatively, for soft constraints, the cost can be integrated into the reward via a penalized reward formulation:

$$\tilde{R}(s, a) = R(s, a) - \beta \cdot C(s, a),$$

where β is a trade-off factor balancing semantic reward and execution latency.

Proposed methodology and solution

We consider a scenario where a central SemCom server broadcast compressed semantic data to heterogeneous User Equipments (UE), including the following items based on the assumption of the common engineering practices:

- Autonomous vehicles, requiring fast, reliable updates within 100 ms;
- Wearable health monitors, accepting relaxed latency of up to 500 ms;
- Emergency drones, which operate under critical constraints and require model decisions within 50 ms.

The server employs a VAE-based semantic encoder-decoder architecture with Joint Source Channel Coding (JSCC) for transmission over wireless channels. Semantic degradation can arise due to domain shift, channel changes, or user-specific feedback. To maintain quality and relevance, the server uses a timing-aware HITL-RL agent to adapt its configuration.

The CMDP for this setting is defined as: $M = (S, A, P, R, C, \gamma, d_i)$, where the definitions of the S, A, P, R, C, γ have been presented in above, while d_i refers to per UE-class timing deadline. Each UE category i imposes the constraint: $E_{\pi_i}[\sum_{t=0}^T C(s_t, a_t)] \leq d_i$. During each decision cycle, the central server performs the following steps:

1. Feedback Collection: Receives semantic quality metrics from UEs (objective or subjective).
2. State Construction: Encodes the current model configuration, UE state, and remaining time budget $b_t = d_i - \sum_{j=0}^{t-1} C(s_j, a_j)$.
3. Action selection: chooses action a_t using a time-aware policy $\pi(s_t)$.
4. Action Validation: Executes the action only if $C(s_t, a_t) \leq b_t$; otherwise, a no-op or safe fallback policy is used.
5. Reward update: Uses a latency-aware reward function:

$$\tilde{R}(s_t, a_t) = R(s_t, a_t) - \beta \cdot C(s_t, a_t)$$

Here, β is a tunable factor to balance semantic gain with latency cost.

Results

The simulation setup consists of a VAE with a 20-dimensional latent space serving as the core semantic model. JSCC is employed for transmission, trained over an additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel and deployed under Rayleigh fading conditions to simulate real-world dynamics. A feedback loop is established in which UEs periodically report semantic quality metrics, which are aggregated and mapped to utility scores. Each candidate action taken by the system has an associated execution latency: updating the knowledge base takes approximately 20 milliseconds, fine-tuning the encoder ranges between 100 and 500 milliseconds, and adjusting training epochs incurs a delay between 50 and 200 milliseconds.

The simulation environment is a simplified abstraction of a time-constrained semantic communication system. Each episode begins with a preset time budget, and the agent must dynamically select among three adaptation actions, updating the knowledge base, fine-tuning the

model, or adjusting training epochs, while balancing the gains in semantic model quality against the latency cost. This environment models external noise and user preference shifts through randomized state transitions, thereby emulating real-world uncertainties in communication channels and user demands. A Deep Q-Network (DQN) is employed to learn an effective policy for action selection under these time constraints. Through repeated interaction, the DQN converges to a policy that maximizes cumulative rewards, carefully choosing the actions that offer the best semantic utility improvements without exceeding the time budget. We repeatedly conducted this simulation using 5 different random seeds, and the DQN training curve is shown in Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6: DQN training curve with different random seeds in the time-constrained SemCom environment.

Conclusions

We presented a timing-constrained HITL-RL framework designed for real-time semantic model adaptation in broadcasting SemCom systems. By formulating the problem as a time-constrained Markov Decision Process, the approach enables latency-aware policy decisions that balance semantic utility with time cost, addressing the diverse timing requirements of heterogeneous UE. The framework supports dynamic adaptation through actions such as knowledge base updates and model fine-tuning, with execution governed by user-specific latency budgets. Simulation results demonstrate that a DQN agent can effectively learn policies that optimize semantic fidelity without violating timing constraints, even under varying channel conditions and feedback uncertainties. Overall, the proposed solution extends conventional HITL-RL by introducing temporal sensitivity, offering a practical foundation for deploying SemCom in time-critical scenarios such as autonomous vehicles, health monitoring, and emergency response.

2.2.2 Personalizing Semantic Communication: A Foundation Model Approach

Context and Motivation

Deep learning (DL)-based semantic communication methods have been extensively investigated. However, the performance of these semantic communication methods is constrained by the naturally limited scalability and generalisability of conventional DL models. The key underlying challenge is that conventional DL models are highly task-specific (i.e., requiring different model architectures and training frameworks), with inevitable performance degradation when faced with heterogeneous data [CC22]. Moreover, existing DL-based methods are only capable of providing generic semantic services (e.g., semantic interpretation and reconstruction),

whether in single-task scenarios [WSB+23], or in multi-user semantic communications [XQT+22]. Consequently, the diverse requirements of users with heterogeneous data cannot be adequately met, thereby resulting in limited generalisability. When extended to new tasks, this task-specific property, which was a key contributor to the robust performance of that specific task, now becomes an inherent limitation on scalability, due to the huge computational overhead required by full model re-training or the need for new model architectures. In essence, solely using conventional DL models for semantic encoders/decoders would not achieve the high scalability and generalisability desired for task-oriented multi-user communications over heterogeneous networks.

Spurred by the same proliferation of massive data, foundation models (FMs), such as large language models, and large vision models, have catalysed many successful applications. The advent of such FMs is particularly significant for semantic communication. In contrast to the smaller conventional DL models, FMs have remarkable capabilities to comprehend and model world knowledge, as well as display new emergent abilities, thereby making them well-suited for achieving scalable and generalised semantic services [WTB+22].

In this context, we propose an FM-based solution for task-oriented multi-user semantic communication systems with personalised semantic services. The proposed framework can provide diverse semantic services for multiple downstream tasks over heterogeneous networks, without introducing ensembles of task-specific models and additional computational overhead for full model re-training.

System Model and Problem statement

We consider a task-oriented multi-user semantic communication system, comprising one base station (BS) and N user equipments (UEs), as shown in Figure 2-7, to perform semantic-aware text/image transmission over noisy wireless channels to accomplish certain tasks (e.g., image/text reconstruction or classification). The transmitter at the BS consists of an FM-based joint source-channel encoder, while personalised FM-based joint decoders are maintained at the receivers of each UE. To achieve collaborative training, an edge server is deployed at the BS for shared model weight aggregation.

Let \mathcal{F}_θ be the FM-based joint encoder, where θ denotes its weight matrix. For each receiver k , let $\mathcal{G}_{w_k}^k$ be the joint decoder, where similarly, the subscript w_k denotes its weight matrix. Given the task of transmitting a data sample s (e.g., an image or a text document), the transmitted signal is given by $x = \mathcal{F}_\theta(s)$. Thus, the received signal at UE k has the form:

$$y_k = h_k x + \xi,$$

where h_k represents the channel gain during the transmission from BS to UE k , and ξ is the additive thermal noise vector, with independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) entries following Gaussian distribution. At the receiver of UE k , the interpreted signal r_k after passing through the corresponding joint decoder is given by $r_k = \mathcal{G}_{w_k}^k(y_k)$.

Proposed framework: We introduce our proposed FM-based semantic communication framework with personalised semantic services. The overall architecture is depicted in Figure 2-7. We discuss the importance of personalized semantic communication and illustrate how personalised semantic services with multiple tasks are realized without updating the pre-trained FMs [CYC+24].

Achieving personalised semantic services: In multi-user semantic communication, DL-based semantic coding typically suffers from performance degradation due to heterogeneous data over distributed networks. Training a generic (i.e., non-personalised) joint semantic encoder/decoder would not satisfy the diverse preferences and requirements of different UEs. Thus, to deal with the divergence across UEs, it is imperative to provide personalised semantic services. This could be achieved by maintaining personalised semantic decoders for each UE according to

local data statistics. FMs are able to generalise well even in the presence of heterogeneous data. However, training FMs directly requires substantial data and computational resources, which is challenging in resource-constrained wireless networks. In view of this, we propose a parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT)-based personalized semantic decoder training framework. This PEFT-based approach allows for fast adaptation to local data. To preserve local data privacy during training, we incorporate federated learning (FL), such that it is suitable for multi-user semantic communication.

Figure 2-7. An illustration of the multi-user semantic communication, in which each UE maintains an FM-based joint decoder with a shared pre-trained FM and personalized adapter.

At receiver k , the semantic decoder is the composition $\mathcal{G}_{w_k}^k := \Psi_k \circ \Phi$, where Φ is the shared pre-trained FM and Ψ_k is the personalised adapter at UE k . We shall denote the weight matrix of Φ (resp. Ψ_k) by ϕ (resp. ψ_k). Note that in the PEFT process, the shared pre-trained FM weights ϕ will be frozen and only the weights of personalised adapters ψ_k will be updated. It is known that training over limited data could easily cause overfitting. To improve the performance of personalised adapters, we propose a personalised FL (pFL) approach. This means training is conducted over a certain number of communication rounds, where in each round, every UE interpolates the local fine-tuned adapter with averaged adapter weights, broadcasted by the edge server at the BS, to obtain personalised adapter weights.

Concretely, training is carried out as follows. In communication round t , each UE performs local fine-tuning (with pre-trained FM weights frozen at both encoder and decoder) to obtain updated adapter weights ψ^t . Next, an aggregated adapter $\bar{\psi}^t$ will be obtained at the BS, in which vanilla FedAvg is adopted for adapter aggregation [MMR+17]. This updated adapter will be broadcasted to local UEs for the next round of local fine-tuning. The detailed algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1.

Note that our proposed framework is task-agnostic and modality agnostic. In particular, the loss function used in LOCALUPDATE is determined by the task. To achieve personalisation locally while still integrating knowledge from other UEs in the system, we propose an interpolation method to balance the trade-off between generic and personalised performances:

$$(\psi_k)^t \leftarrow \alpha \psi_k^{t-1} + (1 - \alpha) \bar{\psi}^{t-1},$$

which is carried out at the beginning of round t , where the input parameter $\alpha \in [0,1]$ is the coefficient to control the degree of personalisation. An illustration of local interpolation is given in Figure 2-8.

Algorithm 1 Personalized partial semantic decoder tuning

Input: α , pre-trained FM ϕ , initialized $\{\psi_k^0\}_{k=1}^N, \bar{\psi}^0$
Output: Personalized adapters $\{\psi_k^T\}_{k=1}^N$

- 1: **for** each round $t = 1$ **to** T **do**
- 2: Select a subset \mathcal{S}_t of UEs
- 3: **for** each client $k \in \mathcal{S}_t$ **do**
- 4: $\psi_k^t \leftarrow \alpha \psi_k^{t-1} + (1 - \alpha) \bar{\psi}^{t-1}$ // adapter interpolation
- 5: $\psi_k^t \leftarrow \text{LOCALUPDATE}(\phi, \psi_k^t)$ // ϕ is fixed
- 6: **end for**
- 7: $\bar{\psi}^t \leftarrow \sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}_t} \frac{|\mathcal{D}_k^t|}{|\mathcal{D}_A^t|} \psi_k^t$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: **return** $\{\psi_k^T\}_{k=1}^N$

Algorithm 1. Personalized partial semantic decoder tuning

To this end, we have elaborated on FM-based semantic coding as well as a pFL-based PEFT approach for providing personalised semantic services, with fast adaptation abilities in different downstream tasks. The proposed framework can achieve scalable semantic communications in a computation-efficient manner, with desirable generalisability over heterogeneous networks.

Figure 2-8: An illustration of pFL-based personalized semantic decoder updating.

Results

The performance of the proposed framework is evaluated with state-of-the-art DL-based semantic communication approaches in diverse tasks, where both text and image transmission tasks are considered with LLaMA-7B and CLIP as FMs [TLI+23], respectively. For datasets, we used Div2K and CIFAR-100 datasets for image recovery and classification tasks [AT17], respectively, as well as SST-2 and Wikitext for text reconstruction and classification tasks [MXB+16]. For heterogeneous data partition of federated training, we adopt the Dirichlet distribution-based method for local training data sampling over $N = 10$ clients with concentration parameter 0.5. Detailed experiment setups can be found in [CYC+24].

Performance comparison: Figure 2-9 gives the results of the averaged Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) performance of our proposed method (i.e. shared CLIP with personalised adapters) over image recovery tasks, and evaluated over different AWGN channel Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs), compared with state-of-the-art baselines DeepJSCC [BKG+19] and WITT [YWD+23]. For the encoders and decoders of our baselines, we used the same architectures

as reported in the respective papers. The figure shows that our proposed method consistently outperforms the baselines across all SNR setups. We also evaluate the performance of sentence reconstruction tasks in Figure 2-10, in which our method (i.e. shared LLaMA-7B with personalised adapters) also achieves better performance with higher sentence similarity compared with DeepSC [XQT+22]. These results demonstrate the superiority of integrating FMs in multi-user semantic communications with personalized semantic services.

Figure 2-9 Averaged PSNR performance vs. SNR over AWGN channel.

Figure 2-10 Averaged sentence similarity vs. SNR over AWGN channel.

Personalisation performance evaluation: In Figure 2-11, we also compared the performance between the personalised and the generic semantic decoding (i.e. each UE shares the same adapter $\bar{\psi}^T$) schemes over 4 different tasks, under the same channel conditions. By this figure, our proposed framework with personalized semantic services demonstrates significant improvements over the generic scheme, in which we used normalized performance as the evaluation metric, where “normalised” refers to the performance with personalised adapters set as 100% in each task for comparison.

Conclusions

We proposed a framework for task-oriented multi-user semantic communication systems with personalised semantic services with the incorporation of FMs. The proposed framework can provide scalable and generalised semantic services over diverse tasks over heterogeneous networks without introducing multiple task-specific full models and additional full model update

computation. Overall, the proposed method provides a new perspective for personalised semantic services in goal-oriented communications, which can also be incorporated with causality-aware semantic representation design and contributes to [6G-GOALS-D4.3].

Figure 2-11 A comparison of the personalised and generic adapter in semantic communications under channel SNR=3dB, in which the normalised performance gap is highlighted.

3 Time framework for networked cyber-physical systems

This section addresses the characterisation of time in networked cyber-physical systems with the development of practical models and frameworks. First, we explore the use of stochastic network calculus in a real Open RAN (O-RAN) network like the one considered in 6G-GOALS, to quantify delay and backlog under realistic traffic conditions. Then, we propose two complementary time-analysis frameworks of increasing complexity. The first one models a one-way communication and focuses on the remote estimation of the process at the transmitter, for which the probabilistic bounds of the estimation error are analysed. The second one introduces a generic closed-loop system that accommodates both periodic and event-triggered feedback, making it suitable for applications such as digital-twin synchronisation and networked control in industrial automation. Taken together, these three works provide a hierarchy of tools for designing and evaluating time-critical cyber-physical systems.

3.1 Delay with stochastic network calculus

Context and motivation

The O-RAN Alliance proposed a novel architecture [UPA+25] embracing and promoting the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) functional split, where each base station is divided across multiple network nodes: Centralized Unit (CU)-Control Plane (CP), CU-User Plane (UP), Distributed Unit (DU) and Radio Unit (RU). Furthermore, the O-RAN architecture considers two RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs), which provide a centralized abstraction of the network, allowing the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) to perform autonomous actions between vBS components and their controllers. Specifically, the non-Real Time (RT) RIC supports large timescale optimization tasks (i.e., in the order of seconds or minutes), including policy computation and Machine Learning (ML) model management. Such functionalities are carried out by third-party applications denominated rApps. Additionally, the near-RT RIC performs RAN optimization, control and data monitoring tasks in near-RT timescales (i.e., from 10ms to 1s). Such functionalities can also be performed by third-party applications denominated xApps. The O-RAN architecture is the baseline for the 6G-GOALS architecture defined in [6G-GOALS-D2.5].

Despite the ongoing standardisation efforts, there are still open challenges toward a successful implementation of the O-RAN architecture: limiting the execution of control tasks in both RICs prevents the use of solutions where decisions must be made in real-time, i.e., below 10 ms

[ORO+22]. For example, ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (uRLLC) Medium Access Control (MAC) scheduling requires making decisions at sub-millisecond timescales [ZAN+21]. Unfortunately, the near-RT-RIC might struggle to accomplish this procedure due to limited access to low-level information (e.g., transmission queues, channel quality, etc.). The potential high latency involved in obtaining this information further exacerbates the problem. This calls for a RT control loop to monitor and orchestrate the decision of MAC schedulers.

In this context, an important yet unaddressed challenge lies in coordinating different control loops, which operate at different time scales. The need for seamless and reliable coexistence of diverse uRLLC services demands effective coordination schemes between the near-RT and non-RT control loops, as well as requires mechanisms to align the decisions made by different control loops while optimizing the resource allocation and avoiding conflicts. In this paper, we advocate for the adoption of Stochastic Network Calculus (SNC) to model the complex dynamics of O-RAN systems and analyse the performance of communications in terms of violation probability, i.e., the probability of a packet being transmitted exceeding a delay bound, while considering the uncertainties and variability in traffic patterns and channel conditions.

In the following we propose **ORANUS**, an O-RAN-compliant mathematical framework to carry out the multi-time-scale control loops for the radio resource allocation to multiple uRLLC services, focusing on near-RT and RT scales. For this orchestration, stochastic network calculus is applied.

System model and problem statement

To perform the near-RT control loop, ORANUS relies on a novel SNC-based controller to compute the amount of guaranteed resource blocks (RBs) for each uRLLC service, which ensures them the violation probability is below a target tolerance. Additionally, the proposed SNC-based controller can directly use real metrics of the incoming traffic and channel conditions to capture their statistical distributions.

ORANUS is designed to manage radio resource allocation for multiple uRLLC services using multi-time-scale control loops

- Near-RT Loop: Operates on 10ms–1s timescales, using an SNC-based controller to compute the number of guaranteed RBs needed for each service to meet its delay targets.
- RT Loop: Works at TTI (Transmission Time Interval) level (~1ms), dynamically adjusting RB allocations based on real-time traffic anomalies detected in transmission queues.

Specifically, as shown in Figure 3-1, ORANUS comprises five xApps and one dApp, as detailed in the following.

- SNC-based Controller xApp: It obtains the guaranteed amount of RBs N_m^{min} for each service $m \in M$, which ensures $P[w > W_m^{th}] < \epsilon_m$, where w is the packet transmission delay, W_m^{th} is the delay budget and ϵ_m is the target violation probability. To this end, it operates every T_{out} Transmission Time Intervals (TTIs) and exchanges information with the Traffic/Cell Capacity Estimator xApps and the RB utilization Estimator xApp.
- Traffic and Cell Capacity Estimator xApps: They analyse each service $m \in M$ and estimate the incoming traffic demand in terms of the number of bits per TTI. Additionally, they compute arrays of samples, each representing the number of bits that each cell can accommodate for these services in an arbitrary TTI, based on the chosen Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCSs) for packet transmission. To that end, these xApps collect these metrics from each DU via the O1 interface.
- RB utilisation Estimator xApp: It estimates the Probability Mass Function (PMF) of the RB utilisation. To that end, it relies on a Neural Network (NN) based on Mixture Density Network (MDN). It considers the following inputs: (a) the incoming traffic demand in each

TTI expressed in bits, (b) the enqueued bits in each TTI and (c) the candidate number of guaranteed RBs for the next T_{out} TTIs. These metrics are available from E2/O1 interfaces.

- **RT Controller dApp:** It operates every TTI and is responsible for ensuring each DU MAC scheduler, one per service $\forall m \in M$, has available at least N_m^{min} PRBs. Note that $\sum_m N_m^{min} \leq N_{cell}^{RB}$, where N_{cell}^{RB} is the RBs available in the cell. Focusing on a single TTI t , if a service m requires a number of RBs N_t such as $N_t < N_m^{min}$, this dApp will allocate N_t RBs to such service. Otherwise, it will first check if there are any available free RBs, i.e., those RBs that were initially allocated to other services but have not been used in the current TTI. If free RBs are found, the dApp allocates N_m^{min} plus the available free RBs to the specified service. Additionally, this dApp monitors the transmission buffers to detect traffic anomalies. If so, it temporarily updates $N_m^{min} \forall m \in M$ to mitigate the violation probability

Figure 3-1 ORANUS Architecture

Proposed methodology and solution

Latency Model based on Stochastic Network Calculus: To avoid introducing clutter in the public deliverable, we refer an interested reader to [AZS+24] for additional details on the mathematical formulation and steps used to derive the following problem formulation. ORANUS applies SNC to compute probabilistic delay bounds. For each service $\forall m \in M$, the packet transmission delay w is defined over a time window (τ, t) using:

- Arrival Process $A(\tau, t)$: Total bits arriving.
- Service Process $S(\tau, t)$: Total bits the system can serve.

Using Exponentially Bounded Burstiness (EBB) and Exponentially Bounded Fluctuation (EBF) models, the arrival and service processes are bounded:

$$P[A(\tau, t) > \alpha(\tau, t)] \leq \epsilon_A,$$

$$P[S(\tau, t) < B(\tau, t)] \leq \epsilon_S$$

With affine bounds:

$$\alpha(\tau, t) = (\rho_A + \delta)(t - \tau) + b_A, \beta(\tau, t) = (\rho_S, \delta) \left[(t - \delta) - \frac{b_S}{\rho_S} \right]$$

The delay bound W is then derived as the horizontal deviation between α and β , i.e., $W = \frac{b_A + b_S}{\rho_S - \delta}$.

This expression provides the worst-case delay under the specified statistical constraints. The controller optimizes θ and δ , which are parameters from the Moment Generating Functions (MGFs) of arrival and service processes, to minimize this bound while satisfying $P[W > W_m^{th}] < \epsilon_m$. The parameters $b_A, b_S, \rho_A, \rho_S, \delta$ are derived using the MGFs of the observed arrival and service distributions, estimated from recent traffic and scheduling behavior.

Resource Allocation and Optimization: Using these delay bounds, ORANUS frames an optimization problem to allocate resources among multiple services. The objective is to minimize the worst-case normalised delay across all $\forall m \in M$ services:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{N_m^{min}} \max_{m \in M} \frac{W_m}{W_m^{th}} \\ & s. t. \sum_{m \in M} N_m^{min} \leq N_{RB}^{cell} \end{aligned}$$

This is a non-convex problem, primarily because W_m depends non-linearly on MGF-derived parameters. To make it tractable, we design Algorithm 2, a heuristic that iteratively adjusts RBs between services by transferring resources from those comfortably within their budget to those nearing violation thresholds.

Algorithm 2: Near-RT RB allocation

```

1 Inputs:  $W_m^{th}, \epsilon_m, \vec{x}_{D_m}, \vec{x}_{C_{m,n}}$ ;
2 Initialization:  $N_{m,z}^{min} = \lfloor N_{cell}^{RB} / |\mathcal{M}| \rfloor, W_m = \infty,$ 
    $W_{m,z} = \infty$   $stop = False$ ;
3 while  $stop == False$  do
4   Estimate  $\pi_{m,n} \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \forall n \in [0, N_{add}]$  [Section IV-B];
5   Estimate  $W_{m,z} \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$  [See Algorithm 1];
6   Evaluate  $g(\vec{W}_z)$  and  $g(\vec{W})$  [See Eq. (24)];
7   if  $g(\vec{W}_z) < g(\vec{W})$  then
8     Update  $N_m^{min} = N_{m,z}^{min}; W_m = W_{m,z} \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$ ;
9     Select  $m' | W_{m'}/W_{m'}^{th} \geq W_m/W_m^{th} \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \setminus \{m'\}$ ;
10    Select  $m'' | W_{m''}/W_{m''}^{th} \leq W_m/W_m^{th} \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \setminus \{m''\}$ ;
11    Compute  $N_{m',z}^{min} = N_{m'}^{min} + 1; N_{m'',z}^{min} = N_{m''}^{min} - 1$ ;
12  else
13     $stop = True$ ;
14  end
15 end
16 return:  $N_m^{min}, W_m$ ;

```

Algorithm 2. Near-RT RB allocation

Results

We perform an exhaustive simulation campaign to validate ORANUS, and evaluate its performance through a Python-based simulator running on a computing platform with 16 GB RAM and a quad-core Intel Core i7-7700HQ @ 2.80 GHz. The simulator considers a single cell using an Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) scheme with $N_{RB}^{cell} \in [50, 100]$ RBs and $t_{slot} = 1$ ms. Regarding the incoming traffic and cell capacity of each uRLLC service, we consider realistic traces collected over an operational RAN using the FALCON tool [FW+19]. The tool allows decoding the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) of a base station, revealing the number of active users and their scheduled resources. To emulate the incoming traffic of three different uRLLC services, we order the active User Equipments (UEs) and split them into equally sized groups, considering their aggregated traffic demand. The resulting PMFs are also displayed in Figure 3-2. For these services, we set a delay budget $W_m^{th} = \{5, 10, 15\}$ ms and target violation probability $\epsilon_m = \{10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}\}$.

We focus on a single decision period of the SNC-based Controller xApp. Specifically, we assume it computes N_m^{min} for the three services. Under this scenario, we evaluate the convergence of the heuristics proposed in Algorithm 2, the computational complexity of such heuristics, and the accuracy of the obtained solution with respect to the optimal. Figure 3-2 shows the convergence of Algorithm 2. Specifically, it depicts the value of the objective function, i.e., purple curve, as well as the values of the ratios $\frac{W_m}{W_m^{th}} \forall m \in M$, i.e., orange, green and red curves, in each iteration. We observe how the proposed heuristics iteratively reduces the objective function until reaching a suboptimal solution. In Figure 3-3, we compare the solution obtained by the proposed heuristics with respect to the optimal one derived by brute force approach when considering $N_{RB}^{cell} \in [50, 100]$ RBs.

Figure 3-2 PMFs of incoming bits from FALCON traces.

The relative error between the two curves is approximately 0.225%, indicating that the proposed solution yields only a 0.225% increase in the worst ratio $\frac{W_m}{W_m^{th}}$ compared to the brute force approach. It is a reasonable deviation given the significant differences in computational complexity among the two approaches as Figure 3-4 shows. Specifically, it summarises the average execution time, the number of iterations, and the resulting ratio as a function of N_{RB}^{cell} . We observe that the number of iterations monotonically increases with N_{RB}^{cell} as the search space (i.e., combinations of RB allocation for each service) is greater, whereas the average execution time for a single iteration slightly decreases. Note that the tasks performed in a single iteration are the same for both approaches.

Figure 3-3 Convergence Analysis of Algorithm 2

Figure 3-4 Performance Analysis of the SNC-based Controller

The execution time per iteration decreases for larger N_{RB}^{cell} values. This is due to the fact that the estimation of W_m (i.e., when Algorithm 2 calls Algorithm 1 — not shown in this summary — in step 5) is faster if more RBs are considered for each service.

N_{cell}^{RB}	60	70	80	90	100
Brute Force (iterations)	1711	2346	3081	3916	4851
Algorithm 2 (iterations)	12	14	16	19	22
Ratio Algorithm 2 / Brute Force	142.58	167.57	192.56	206.10	220.5
Avg. Execution Time per iteration (ms)	184.62	179.09	176.39	173.76	171.85

Figure 3-5 Computational Complexity Comparison

3.2 Semantic communications in control systems

Context and motivation

Accurate and timely state estimation is crucial for the effective control of dynamic systems, such as those found in autonomous driving and industrial automation [JCZ+21]. These systems rely heavily on continuous monitoring and quick response capabilities, making the precision of state estimations a cornerstone for safety and efficiency. However, the reliability of these estimations is often compromised by the limitations imposed by wireless communication environments, including bandwidth constraints and channel fading [TV05].

To address these challenges, we introduce the concept of semantic over-the-air (SemOTA) aggregation, a novel approach that prioritises the transmission of critical sensor data over wireless networks. This methodology ensures that only the most pertinent measurements influencing the system's real-time state are communicated, significantly reducing unnecessary network traffic and enhancing the spectral efficiency. By focusing on the semantic importance of data, SemOTA enables more accurate and power-efficient state estimations, aligning with the stringent demands of modern control systems.

System model and problem statement

We consider a remote state estimation system which consists of a dynamic plant, multiple sensors and a remote state estimator, as shown in the following Figure 3-6. The sensors monitor the plant state and deliver the state measurements to the remote state estimator via the unreliable wireless network. The remote state estimator generates the state estimation based on the received noisy measurements from the wireless network. We consider a time-slotted system where the dynamic plant is modelled by a set of coupled first-order linear difference equations for the state variables $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times 1}$, given by

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + w_k,$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times S}$ defines the plant dynamics, and $w_k \sim N(0_{S \times 1}, W)$ represents zero-mean Gaussian plant noise with a positive definite covariance matrix $W \in S_{++}^S$. The initial plant state is denoted as $x_0 = x(0) \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times 1}$.

Figure 3-6: Typical architecture of a remote state estimation system over a wireless network.

We consider $M \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ geographically distributed sensors monitoring the dynamic plant. Each sensor is equipped with $N_t \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ transmission antennas and utilizes a shared radio pool to achieve high spectral efficiency. The connection between the dynamic plant and the wireless sensors is characterized by:

$$z_{m,k} = C_m x_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1,$$

where $C_m \in \mathbb{R}^{N_t \times S}$ is the observation matrix of the m -th sensor, defining how it accesses the plant state x_k . The measurement collected by the m -th sensor at time k is denoted as $z_{m,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_t \times 1}$. The communication link between the sensors and the remote state estimator is modelled as a $N_r \times N_t$ wireless MIMO fading channel. Each active sensor transmits its state measurement $z_{m,k}$ via OTA aggregation. The received signal y_k is an aggregation of the noisy sensor measurements, given by:

$$y_k = \sum_{m=1}^M \delta_{m,k} H_{m,k} z_{m,k} + v_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1,$$

where $H_{m,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_t}$ represents the MIMO channel fading gain, which remains constant within each timeslot and is independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.) across sensors and

timeslots. Each element of $H_{m,k}$ follows a zero-mean Gaussian distribution with unit covariance. $v_k \sim N(0_{N_r \times 1}, I_{N_r})$ denotes additive noise at the remote state estimator, while $\delta_{m,k} \in \{0,1\}$ is the sensor scheduling variable.

The objective of the remote state estimator is to compute the minimum mean square error (MMSE) estimate of the plant state x_k based on y_0, \dots, y_k . This can be achieved via Kalman filtering and omitted here.

Proposed methodology and solution

For efficient remote state estimation, we propose a SemOTA-based sensor scheduling policy that dynamically balances power efficiency and state estimation accuracy within the OTA framework. Specifically, we formulate the sensor scheduling problem as follows:

$$\min_{\pi} E \left[\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} Tr(\Sigma_k) + \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma Tr(\delta_{m,k} C_m C_m^T) + Tr(\Sigma_K) \right],$$

where $\pi = \pi_{k:k} = 0, 1, \dots, K-1$ denotes the sensor scheduling policy over the horizon of K steps, with $\pi_k = \{\delta_{1,k}, \dots, \delta_{M,k}\}$ representing the sensor activation decisions at each k -th time step, and γ is a trade-off parameter that balances estimation accuracy and power consumption. $\Sigma_k \in S^{S \times S}$ is the prior error covariance at the remote state estimator.

By solving the above scheduling problem, we show that the optimal sensor scheduling solution has a semantic structure in the sense that $\delta_{m,k} = 1$ only if its transmission significantly enhances the estimation performance, measured by a small value of the term Σ_{k+1} given Σ_k .

Results

We verify the advantages of our semantic over-the-air (SemOTA) aggregation framework by comparing it with conventional baselines that include measure-threshold-based sensor activation (Baseline 1), error-covariance-threshold-based sensor activation (Baseline 2), and full sensor activation (Baseline 3). These baselines represent common strategies in remote state estimation, where full sensor activation does not discriminate between data based on its relevance, leading to higher power consumption, and threshold-based activation which triggers sensor responses based on predefined data significance thresholds, potentially overlooking critical dynamic changes. Specifically, we compare the normalised mean square error (NMSE) as well as power consumption, as depicted in Figure 3-7 and Figure 3-8, respectively.

Figure 3-7 illustrates the NMSE comparisons, showing that the SemOTA framework consistently achieves lower errors compared to the baselines across a variety of network conditions. This improvement is indicative of the framework's ability to transmit only the most relevant information, thus enhancing the accuracy of the state estimations.

Figure 3-8 demonstrates the power consumption across these methods. It is evident from the figure that SemOTA significantly reduces the power usage by up to 30%, compared to the baseline schemes. This reduction is crucial for deployments in energy-constrained environments, proving the effectiveness of our approach in conserving energy while maintaining high data integrity.

Conclusions

In this work, we proposed a novel sensor scheduling framework for remote state estimation over wireless MIMO fading channels, leveraging semantic over-the-air (SemOTA) aggregation. By formulating the scheduling problem as a finite-horizon stochastic optimization, we derived both an optimal solution and a computationally efficient approximation that selects sensor measurements based on their semantic relevance to the estimation task. The proposed approach dynamically adapts to real-time variations in the system state and channel conditions, enabling the transmission of only the most informative sensor data and thereby achieving an effective

trade-off between estimation accuracy and power consumption. Numerical results demonstrate that SemOTA significantly outperforms conventional baselines in both estimation performance and energy efficiency, validating its practical potential for real-world wireless control applications. These findings underscore the promise of semantic communication in enabling scalable and resource-efficient designs for networked control systems. Furthermore, our work also contributes to [6G-GOALS-D4.3], as the dynamic system state in our model evolves according to a Markov process. This inherently causal structure ensures that the proposed scheduling policy is based on past and present data, aligning with the core principles of causal semantic processing and decision-making.

Figure 3-7: Normalised state estimation MSE versus the number of sensors.

Figure 3-8. Total transmission power versus timeslot.

3.3 Unified Timing Analysis for Closed-Loop Goal-Oriented Wireless Communication

Context and motivation

Goal-oriented paradigms require demanding closed-loop interactions with strict timing requirements, starting from the commands transmitted by the user and ending with the reception of feedback. The closed-loop interactions are common in several of the typical 6G scenarios considered by the 3GPP, including remote control, virtual social, and gaming. Some of them appear also in the use cases of 6G-GOALS [6G-GOALS-D2.1].

Compared to the point-to-point perspective that has dominated the literature, the analysis of closed-loop communications over fading channels presents additional challenges. In the case of timing, there are multiple random factors related to the communication/computation latency and the heterogeneity of feedback mechanisms across multi-modal sensing data. The goal of this contribution, initially presented in [LKP+25], is to develop a unified timing-analysis framework for closed-loop goal-oriented communications (CGC) over wireless channels. Given the highly mathematical nature of the original work, we refer the reader to [LKP+25] for the full analytical derivations and formal proofs. In this summary, we focus instead on describing the general system model, the key components of the proposed solution, and the main insights derived from the evaluations.

System model and problem formulation

The system model is depicted in Figure 3-9. The figure shows a step-by-step example of the remote-control operation with the assistance of Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), semantic information, and Digital Twin (DT). Multiple communication and computation processes are included in the closed-loop, representing a high range of applications and scenarios.

Figure 3-9. System model for a general CGC system

The system model comprises a base station (BS), a user equipment (UE), and a remote agent (RA) equipped with a sensor. The UE and the RA communicate over a wireless channel via the BS, using dedicated channel resources. Additionally, the BS is equipped with a MEC server to perform computation tasks, including feature extraction and decompression.

The following three types of data are defined in the system:

- **Control data** is transmitted sporadically by the UE as high-level (HL) commands. Like in the example of Figure 3-8 this can be, for example, data that represents the UE's intention to place the yellow box on the red one. The HL commands are subject to a random processing delay at the BS where, for example, a large language model (LLM) assists in the process of semantic information extraction.
- **Periodic-Feedback (PF) data** is collected at fixed, short intervals every T_S seconds. The PF data is queued at both the RA and the BS. PF data is typically small in size and represents numeric values, such as the speed of the RA or the temperature.
- **Event-Triggered (ET) data** is generated by the RA in response to a low-level (LL) command. ET data is generally throughput-intensive and may include multimedia data such

as video, tactile details, and audio. The RA first compresses the ET data with a compression ratio κ before transmitting it to the BS. The MEC server decompresses the data, extracts valuable information (VI) such as the location and texture of the objective, and updates its DT model in preparation for the next hop.

The communication flow of these three types of data is shown in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-10. Diagram of the components of the closed-loop latency

The goal is then to analyse the closed-loop latency T of a single transmission round under various constraints of the individual links. The notation to describe this latency is as follows. The transmission latency of the PF data is given by

$$T_{PF} = T_{PF1}^q + T_{PF1}^{cm} + T_{PF2}^q + T_{PF2}^{cm}$$

where T_{PF1}^q and T_{PF1}^{cm} denote the queuing and transmission delays from the RA to the BS, respectively, and T_{PF2}^q and T_{PF2}^{cm} the queuing and transmission delays from the BS to the UE, respectively. Similarly for the control data we write

$$T_{CL} = T_{HL}^{cm} + T_{LL}^{cp} + T_{LL}^{cm}$$

where T_{HL}^{cm} and T_{LL}^{cm} denote the transmission delay of the HL command and the LL command, respectively, and T_{LL}^{cp} denotes the processing delay at the BS. Third, the ET latency from the RA to the UE is written

$$T_{ET} = T_{ET}^c + T_{CD}^{cm} + T_{ET}^d + T_{VI}^{cp} + T_{VI}^{cm}$$

where T_{ET}^c denotes the compression delay at the RA, T_{CD}^{cm} and T_{VI}^{cm} are the transmission delays from the RA to the BS and from the BS to the UE, respectively, and T_{ET}^d and T_{VI}^{cp} denote the decompression delay and the processing delay at the BS, respectively. The goal is to characterise the closed-loop operation, i.e., from the generation time of the HL command until the reception of both the corresponding ET data and the PT data generated closest in time to the generation time of the ET data. The latency of the feedback link T_{FL} can be approximated by

$$T_{FL} \approx \max T_{PF} + T_{ET}$$

And the closed-loop latency is finally written as

$$T = T_{CL} + T_{FL}$$

$t_{ii} \in HL, LL, PF1, PF2, CD, VI$ denotes the time to transmit a given packet and, without loss of generality, we consider $t_{CD} = t_{VI} = t_u$. With the aim of having the most generic possible framework,

the cube in 3-10 illustrates the configuration/operation options included in the analysis. In the jitter-latency/constraints axis, both average and tail-based constraints on jitter and latency are considered. Average-based constraints are related to the expectation of timing metrics, while tail-based constraints are related to the violation probability of timing metrics. For the CL, both configurations with and without a latency constraint are considered. In the FL, the PF data may or may not relay on Channel State Information known at both receiver and transmitter (CSIRT) and frequency or spatial diversity (FSD). Based on these constraints along each axis, the different options are combined to generate the eight vertices.

Figure 3-11. Configurations for the unified CGC framework

Considering all these elements, the unified optimization problem for the CGC system is formulated as follows

$$\min \varepsilon d(T) + (1 - \varepsilon)g(P_{avg}, B)$$

where $\varepsilon \in [0,1]$ and $g(P_{avg}, B)$ is the objective function related to power and bandwidth resources. The problem is subject to the vertex constraints of Figure 3-11, and power constraints and bandwidth constraints.

Methodology and solution

There are both discrete and continuous random variables in the defined problem. The methodology consists of calculating, first of all, the PDFs and CDFs of the different latency components in each of the vertices and with the help of saddle point approximations (SPA) where needed. SPA is a powerful method to approximate complicated distributions with high accuracy guarantees while avoiding intractable computations. A central indicator of the goodness of the SPA is the error analysis. In the literature, this can be done for i.i.d. random variables. For cases in which higher approximation accuracy was needed, second-order SPA has been applied. Moreover, continuous approximations are given for large number of packets or small transmission time of a packet, using the central limit theorem to approximate the sum of communication latency as normal random variables.

Once the distributions are obtained, the optimization problem is solved for specific configurations. Specifically, the optimization of the compression ratio κ and transmission powers of the periodic feedback and control data is presented in detail, while treating the bandwidth and other transmission powers as fixed. This corresponds to the problem in vertex 8.

Results

The proposed framework is validated through Monte Carlo simulations and numerical results. First, Figure 3-12 (a) shows the approximated CDFs versus the simulation for the total closed-

loop latency T and different compression ratios κ , whereas (b) plots the corresponding approximation errors. The four columns correspond to different scenarios: general case, large number of packets, small t_u and small number of packets, large t_u and small number of packets. The last case is the most extreme scenario, and this is visible in the discrepancies of the two possible approximations. In any case, the tail of the distribution (percentile 99%) exhibits an absolute error in the order of 10^{-5} for the first three columns and 10^{-4} in the last case.

Figure 3-12. Validation of (a) the approximated CDFs of the total latency T ; (b) and approximation errors of the total latency T . Column 1 corresponds to the general scenario, column 2 is with a large number of packets, column 3 with a small t_u and small number of packets, and column 4 is the extreme scenario with a small number of packets and large t_u .

Finally, Figure 3-13 illustrates the optimal power-latency trade-off in the system. The power consumption is higher with a smaller τ_{PF} , which is the hard deadline for PF data. This is because a smaller τ_{PF} refers to larger PF transmission power ($P_{PF1} + P_{PF2}$) and it imposes stricter requirements on the ET latency, which results in a larger power of the control data (P_{CD}). These results may provide instructions for the choices in the system parameters.

Figure 3-13. Power-latency trade-off in the CGC system

Conclusions

This contribution presents a unified timing-analysis for generic goal-oriented closed-loop systems. The multi-modal feedback is divided into PF and ET data covering a wide range of scenarios. The randomness of computation, compression and communication were incorporated as well. The generalisation of the approximation for the conditional expectation of timing metrics makes this general analysis the basis for future system optimizations.

4 Joint optimization of data acquisition, information, and reconstruction

This section presents analysis and evaluation of SemCom resource optimizations that consider the data acquisition, information processing and transmission, and reconstruction. The focus is on three challenging applications/scenarios: (1) IoT applications with heterogeneous sensors that use push-/pull-based communication; (2) Digital Twins leveraging networked cyber-physical systems; (3) V2X communications. For each of them, the analysis and evaluations demonstrate the significant gains of applying SemCom and GO principles to the designs, particularly in terms of energy saving that are obtained without jeopardizing the system performance, especially in terms of time and task completion.

4.1 Joint optimizations in push-/pull-based communication

Context and motivation

In IoT networks, there are two possible communication modes:

- Push-based communication, in which IoT devices generate data and autonomously decide when and what to transmit to the BS. This is the classical approach of communications.
- Pull-based communication, in which the BS actively initiates data retrieval from IoT devices, strategically deciding when to query and which devices to address.

The pull-based communication has gained attention in the last years driven by the rapid expansion and diversification of IoT deployments. As applications become more heterogeneous, with varying latency, reliability, and energy constraints, the pull-based model offers advantages in terms of network coordination, energy savings, and scalability. This is also related to closed-loop IoT traffic, such as the one in which the intelligent nodes at the network are purposefully pulling data from the IoT devices by sending queries and thereby requesting transmissions. In the literature, pull-based has been analysed in relation to new timing metrics that consider the query process, such as the Query Age of Information (QAoI) [CHK+22], [YU+23]. On the other hand, the technology enabler for low-energy pull-based IoT communication is the wake-up radio, an ultra-low power wake-up receiver (WuR) installed into the IoT devices that remains active waiting for specific wake-up signals (WuSs) while the higher energy-demanding main radio is turned off [PMK+17]. The design of the WuSs is currently studied in 3GPP, which considers a solution based on unique identities of the devices embedded in the wake-up signals transmitted by the BS, namely, ID-based WuSs. This idea may result in wasteful wake-up of nodes which might transmit data irrelevant to the current task. In a goal-oriented optimization, it is more interesting to define a Content-based Wake-up (CoWu) [SYH+21], such that the information about the data needed by the BS is embedded into the WuS, letting only the nodes having suitable readings turn on their main radio and transmit.

Nevertheless, employing pull-based communication only could lead to loss of data retrieval because the BS does not have the same “local” knowledge of the IoT nodes. For example, the BS will not know if a device incurs in an anomaly, because only the device itself is informed about its own measurements; without push-based communication, the device has to wait to inform the

BS until it receives a WuS, possibly leading to high delay in information retrieval which is particularly dangerous for critical events, such as anomalies or component failures.

To overcome this issue, the co-existence of push and pull communications in heterogeneous IoT scenarios was presented in [6G-GOALS-D2.1], showing that it poses challenges in resource allocation and energy efficiency. Efficient management of this coexistence is crucial for optimizing network performance and prolonging device battery life. In the literature, only a limited number of studies ([PSX+2021], [TMC+24]) have explored the interaction of push- and pull-based, but as inter-dependent processes. Instead, the motivation for this study is their co-existence as independent processes in a 6G network. The two 6G-GOALS papers that support this contribution are [SCP+24] and [CSS+24].

System model and problem statement

The system comprises a BS and multiple IoT devices employing either pull-based or push-based communication. Indexes q and p are for pull and push, respectively. The push-based devices transmit data using random access methods.

For the pull-based devices, we consider two possible scenarios depending on the available technology at the receiver. (1) Scenario 1 (IDWu): the baseline scenario assumes they are equipped with WuRs that remain in low-power mode until activated by an ID-based wake-up signal (IDWu) from the BS. (2) Scenario 2 (CoWu): the advanced case, instead, proposes CoWu for the BS to remotely activate only a subset of pull-based nodes equipped with wake-up receivers, based on the relevance of the information. This is enabled by the WuSs, which carry information about the data needed by the BS. The two scenarios have many analogies in the system model and goals, as explained in the following.

Scenario 1: IDWu

The system operates in a time-slotted framework analogous to 5G where frames (T_{frame}) and slots (τ) define the time domain. Frames contain F slots of fixed duration τ , such that $\tau F = T_{frame}$. In Scenario 1, there are two segments, T_{pull} and T_{push} , corresponding to the duration of the push and pull, respectively, leading to the proposed time-frame structure in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1. Frame structure for the pull/push co-existence in Scenario 1

Queries dictating the ID of the device to pull and the deadline for the retrieved data arrive from the cloud following a Poisson Point Process (PPP) of rate λ_q . At the start of each frame, the BS aggregates queries received in the previous frame and schedules transmission in FIFO order. Push nodes, on the other hand, generate data according to a PPP of rate λ_p .

Scenario 2: CoWu

In Scenario 2, there is additional flexibility in the time frame by defining dedicated slots only for pull but also shared slots that can be used by both pull and push. Specifically, the UL portion of the frame is divided into two parts: τ_w slots reserved for pull and τ_u shared slots.

Figure 4-2. Frame structure for the pull/push co-existence in Scenario 2

Moreover, all devices employ a p-persistent Carrier Sense Multiple Access (CSMA): when a device attempts to access the channel, it first conducts carrier sensing at the beginning of a slot. If the channel is idle, the node attempts transmission of its packet with transmission probability p . An error-free ACK is received immediately from the BS after each successful transmission. The nodes detecting a packet loss by the absence of the ACK retransmit their packets following p-persistent CSMA. Two types of collisions may happen: intra-class and inter-class collisions. The former happens among the data transmission operating in the same communication mode (pull with pull, or push with push), whereas the latter happens among the nodes operating in different modes. The BS controls the ratio between the slots reserved for pull and shared by tuning the parameter $\alpha \in [0,1]$.

Proposed methodology and solutions

Scenario 1: IDWu

In Scenario 1, the BS must balance the allocation of time slots between the two communication modes, considering the competing goals: maximize the average number of successfully served queries (pull) and maximize the UL throughput (push). The equation that describes the general trade-off is (cf. Figure 4-1):

$$T_{push} = T_{frame} - T_{pull} = (F - Q(k_w + k_t))\tau$$

where Q are the number of queries served per frame, and k_w, k_t are the slots for WuS/radio activation and for data transmission, respectively. As Q increases, more queries can be fulfilled, and fewer slots remain for push.

The two KPIs, queries and UL push throughput, are calculated using standard communication models. For the success probability of serving the queries, the scenario is modelled with a multi-server queueing model with null queueing capacity, i.e., M/D/Q/0 using Kendall's notation. The solution of this model is written in terms of the Erlang-B formula for discarding probability when the number of sources is infinite. For the UL push throughput, the calculation is based on the framed ALOHA theory. Instead of treating them separately, the weighted average success probability for the communication coexistence is proposed and used for the optimization:

$$p_s = w_q p_s^{(q)} + w_p p_s^{(p)}$$

where w_q and w_p are positive weights and $p_s^{(q)}$ and $p_s^{(p)}$ the success probabilities. Since both $p_s^{(q)}$ and $p_s^{(p)}$ depend on Q , it is possible to find the value of Q that maximises p_s . Framed-ALOHA with grant-free random access is assumed, such that collisions lead to packet loss, as no HARQ or retransmissions are considered.

Scenario 2: CoWu

In Scenario 2, the considered task for the pull devices is to monitor an independent and identically distributed physical random process whose value is assumed to be approximately constant

during the frame duration. A target range threshold V_{th} for this monitored process is embedded in the CoWu signal for the so-called range-query, consisting of a lower and an upper limit of the range.

While Scenario 1 addresses the throughput, Scenario 2 focuses on the total energy consumption of the system and aims at deriving the access mechanism for reducing such energy consumption for pull devices while satisfying the requirements of both push and pull nodes. The methodology consists in doing the analysis of the distribution of successful transmissions, considering a Markov chain in which each state represents the number of packets available for transmission. The push success probability is impacted by the pull devices, as each push having a packet to deliver starts transmitting at the beginning of a shared slot, contending the channel with active push and pull devices who have not completed data transmission. The energy consumption for pull devices is a function of the amount of time spent in the transmit and receive states. Moreover, the accuracy of pull retrieved data γ_w is written as

$$\gamma_w = Pr(T = S)$$

where T denotes the subset of pull devices observing the process within the target range threshold, and S the subset of pull devices successfully transmitting the data by the end of the frame.

Results

Scenario 1: IDWu

The results in Figure 4-3 show the behaviour of the weighted average success probability as function of the number of queries per slot Q (left) and push/pull arrival rates λ_p / λ_q (right). As expected, when the number of queries increases, the maximum p_s is obtained for a larger Q . Moreover, is a monotonically decreasing function of both λ_p and λ_q . These figures provide analytical results to design the frame when push and pull traffic must co-exist.

Figure 4-3. (a) Success probability versus number of queries per slot; (b) Success probability versus push arrival rate

Scenario 2: CoWu

For Scenario 2, the optimal value of α is first obtained from this optimization problem:

$$\alpha_{opt}(\lambda) = arg_{\alpha} \min E_{tot}(V_{th}, \lambda, \alpha) p_s^{qpq}$$

This optimal value is plot in Figure 4-4 (a) against the rate λ and different values of query target range. The optimal value decreases with λ as the BS needs to increase the time τ_u dedicated to be shared among all the devices. Then, Figure 4-4 (b) quantifies the energy efficiency η of the goal-oriented approach by plotting the energy efficiency of CoWu versus a conventional RR. Only feasible values of η are plotted. As λ increase, the energy efficiency η increases, because the pull devices experience more inter-class collisions. Furthermore, η becomes larger as the

range of requested content becomes larger. The results demonstrate that the CoWu mechanism achieves up to a 38% improvement in energy efficiency for pull-based devices compared to traditional scheduling methods.

Figure 4-4 (a) Optimal push/pull sharing versus system load; (b) Energy consumption ratio between CoWu and RR approaches versus system load

Conclusions

The analyses in this contribution, validated through simulations, highlight the interdependence of push and pull communication modes and the need of adjusting the time allocation reserved for each to achieve optimal performance in terms of throughput, task-accuracy and energy. Based on the knowledge of the incoming push and pull traffic, the time allocation that optimally balances the overall performance in a single frame has been found. If an advanced CoWu is considered, then the energy consumption is highly reduced by defining a task-oriented query that avoids unnecessary wakes-up of nodes.

4.2 Joint optimizations in Digital Twins

Context and motivation

The advent of Industry 4.0's intelligent manufacturing paradigm requires the acquisition of substantial real-time data volumes from a diverse array of wireless sensors. In contrast to conventional simulation tools or optimization methodology, digital twin (DT) models enable the transformation of these extensive datasets into predictive models, supporting novel real-time interactions and decision-making for system operators. The DT was presented in the use cases of 6G-GOALS ([6G-GOALS-D2.1]). For wireless network control systems (WNCS), the DT is an enabler for advanced network intelligence and automation, with dynamic, data-driven, and closed-loop control mechanisms. However, building and maintaining and up-to-date DT is not an easy task, especially in dynamic and large-scale network environments, which are the focus of this work.

In practical deployments, a DT must ingest, process, and fuse a large volume of heterogeneous data streams, often with stringent freshness and latency constraints. The complexity of the modelled system, combined with the high-dimensional and time-varying nature of the inputs, necessitates the use of efficient and scalable ML techniques. To ensure robust and generalizable performance, DT models typically require training on a combination of synthetically generated data and real-world measurements, leveraging domain knowledge and statistical modelling to fill gaps in observability.

Moreover, maintaining synchronization between the physical system and its digital replica is a critical requirement. The DT must be continuously updated in near real time to reflect changes in the state of the physical system, which places significant demands on the underlying com-

munication infrastructure in terms of reliability, latency, and bandwidth efficiency. These challenges are exacerbated in wireless IoT settings, where connectivity is intermittent, and resources are constrained. The contribution described here and detailed in [BPS+24] addresses these challenges with a task-oriented approach, with the focus on the operation of the DT in WNCS under communication timing requirements.

System model and problem statement

The considered scenario (Figure 4-5) is a WNCS with sensor devices that represents the physical world, alongside a DT (the digital world) that is situated in a 5G network. The DT is responsible for gathering data from the physical world, either periodically or adaptively, which is subsequently utilized to optimize a model capturing the underlying physical dynamics.

Figure 4-5. The considered architecture with a DT

The physical world consists of a single primary agent (PA) and a set of sensing agents (SAs). The PA operates within a K -dimensional process that represents the state of the environment. The SAs are responsible for observing the environment and establishing communication with the access point (AP), which transmits the information to the DT. A query interval (QI) is defined to maintain the synchronization and consistency of the DT. Specifically, at each QI, each SA receives a D -dimensional observation, with $D \leq K$. This observation is linearly dependent on the system state. With these premises, the DT predicts the PA's state, devises an optimal policy for scheduling the SAs, and generates optimal suggestions for subsequent actions. This information is used by the AP to execute appropriate actions in the physical world.

The key timing KPI used in this work is the Age of Loop (AoL), introduced in [6G-GOALS-D2.2]. This metric captures the freshness of a closed-loop communication like the one addressed here. Its behaviour is shown in Figure 4-6, where the AoL starts at the downlink, grows linearly over time and drops at the time instances where the loop is closed to the corresponding timestamp in which the state feedback of a new control signal was generated. Besides, the model defines also all the time contributors of the system, encompassing communication, control, and computation elements. T_{config} is the time the DT model requires to update the active state of SAs, and it consists of the SA's state sync, the state estimation, the policy updating, the action computing, and the SA scheduling. The predicted estimator \hat{s}_t of state s_t is modeled with

$$p(s_t) \sim N(\hat{s}_t, \Psi_t), n \in N$$

where the covariance matrix will be updated at QI t according to the Extended Kalman Filter.

Figure 4-6. Timing diagram of signals and behaviour of the Age of Loop (AoL)

The MSE of the estimator is then

$$MSE = E[\|s_s - \hat{s}_t\|_2^2], n \in N$$

With this system model, the primary objective of the DT is to keep a precise assessment of the state of a PA and, based on that, decide the sequence of actions to be executed in the physical world based on its beliefs about states. Specifically, we define the value function of controlling PA under control policy π , and we aim at jointly minimizing the sum PRB consumption and delivering optimal control signals. We refer to [BPS+24] for the mathematical details.

To demonstrate the performance of the DT, the selected task for the system is the problem known as Mountain Car MDP, a deterministic MDP that consists of a car placed stochastically at the bottom of a sinusoidal valley, with the only possible actions being the accelerations that can be applied to the car in either direction. The goal of the MDP is to strategically accelerate the car to reach the goal state on top of the right hill.

Proposed methodology and solution

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is used for finding the optimal control policy. While RL algorithms are commonly formulated in terms of Markov Decision Processes (MDPs), real-life applications work often with states that are unobservable directly. This is the case of the described application, for which we consider a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP).

For training the policy π , Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) is applied. An actor-critic structure involves dividing the model into two distinct components, harnessing the strengths of value-based and policy-based methods. Specifically, the actor is primarily responsible for estimating the policy, which dictates the agent's actions in a given state, while the critic is dedicated to estimating the value function, which predicts the expected future reward for a particular state or state-action pair. A modified reward is defined to reflect the two-fold objective of the agent: to maximize the original reward, maximizing the value function of controlling PA, while simultaneously minimizing the cost associated with the observations.

The proposed solution, denoted as AoL-REVERB, consists of two parts: (1) one algorithm that takes control actions applied to the physical world and effectively managing the observation errors received from SAs; (2) and the SA scheduling algorithm to find the optimal PRB assignment to the most significant SAs observing the signals, for which the AoL is integrated into the algorithm.

Results

To illustrate the performance of the selected task of a Mountain Car MDP, the proposed AoL-REVERB algorithm is compared with several benchmarks: (1) a Perfect algorithm that allows

DT to get the observation of the next state without any error; (2) a cost-based greedy (CB-Greedy) in which the AP queries all nearest SAs based on ascending order of distance from AP to SA; (3) an error-based greedy (EB-Greedy) that relies on the decreasing confidence levels of SAs; (4) a Traditional scheme where the RL agent gets noise observation from one SA every QI.

Figure 4-7 shows the environment and trajectory with coordinated control force. In this evaluation, the goal is for the car to reach the target position at 0.45. It is observed that the AoL-REVERB's and the Perfect algorithm meet the trajectory goal 75 QIs. On the contrary, the trained network with the Traditional algorithm must use up to 2x number of steps to reach the goal. The conclusion is that precise knowledge of the car's position and velocity at all times is not necessary for implementing suitable control forces.

Figure 4-7. The environment and trajectory with coordinated control force of different schemes

Next, Figure 4-8 illustrates the good trade-off achieved by the proposed AoL-REVERB. In Figure 4-8 (a) (left), the consumed PRB and MRMSE are shown and demonstrate that the proposal consumes less resources (2900 PRB) while achieving the same MRMSE as compared to CB-Greedy and EB-Greedy. On Figure 4-8 (b), we plot a snapshot of the uncertainty evolution and the strategic selection of SAs. It is observed that the DT only requests more observations when the DT threshold is surpassed or when the RL agent necessitates high precision, typically when the agent is nearing its goal and precise force control is imperative.

Figure 4-8. (a) Consumed PRB and MRMSE; (b) Snapshot of AoL-REVERB uncertainty evolution and no. of selected SAs vs. QI

Conclusions

The proposed framework identifies the Age of Loop (AoL) metric as a key optimization GO metric that captures latency, reliability and timeliness in wireless networked control systems. Specifically, the scenario is formulated in terms of a Digital Twin (DT) where sensors provide observations to build a DT model of the underlying system dynamics, integrating sensing, control, computing, and communications in a closed-loop system. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposal can meet the task performance while halving the communication overhead.

4.3 Joint optimizations in V2X communication

Context and motivation

This contribution investigates the application of semantic and goal-oriented optimizations in Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) scenarios, with the focus on the joint optimization of data acquisition, information, and reconstruction for the transmission of images.

V2X is a communication technology that enables vehicles to interact with each other, infrastructure, pedestrians, and networks to improve road safety, traffic efficiency, and autonomous driving. Due to the high number of resource-hungry applications and limited bandwidth, it is expected that SemCom becomes the key enabler to make future Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) feasible. In particular, the transmission of images from vehicular sensors is crucial for real-time traffic awareness and safety. However, conventional transmission methods struggle to meet the stringent latency and reliability requirements of ITS due to bandwidth limitations. Semantic Communications (SemCom) and goal-oriented communications emerge as a promising solution by transmitting only meaningful information rather than entire images, significantly reducing the data load while preserving essential content for decision-making in vehicular networks.

Figure 4-9. Example of the use of SemCom for image transmission in V2X networks

A representative use case is shown in Figure 4-9 where a vehicle informs nearby vehicles with a limited vision about an obstacle in the road to avoid a possible collision. By having vehicles send images they capture, it is possible to extend the awareness of the nearby vehicles, having a clear positive impact in safety.

Compression lies at the core of source coding. Conventional compression techniques, such as MJPEG and H.265/HEVC, reduce image size but do not prioritize semantically important information, in contrast to more recent semantic algorithms that further reduce the total transmission without jeopardizing the system performance. As an example, that serves as the starting point of this study, the tradeoff between latency and image refresh rate in a V2X scenario is illustrated in Figure 4-10.

Figure 4-10. Latency of classical and semantic source coding

Raw data and MJPEG compression with three different levels of quality is compared with the semantic segmentation proposed in [ZD24], called RealtimeSeg, tailored for edge computing platforms and real-time. It is observed that SemCom is able to greatly increase the maximum supported load (i.e., the maximum refresh rate with finite latency). As a reference, the dataset in [CIT25] consists of video frames captured by sensors working at 17 Hz refresh rate.

Motivated by this, this study aims to integrate and evaluate existing SemCom algorithms, not only for semantic compression but also for intelligent filtering and data selection, in a V2X system. The papers [GLP24a] and [GLP24b] elaborate the content of this subsection.

System model and problem statement

An ITS scenario where vehicles capture and transmit image data for real-time traffic management is considered. The primary challenge lies in efficiently transmitting these images over bandwidth-constrained V2X network while maintaining low latency and high reliability. The on-board unit (OBU) in the vehicle receives information from N sensors (see Figure 4-11) that continuously generate information with rate R_i , where $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. The access network has available capacity R_W , not sufficient to transmit the raw data. When congestion happens, a classical communication will drop some random packets.

Figure 4-11. System model for V2X networks

The wireless V2X channel is modelled as a block Rayleigh fading channel where the channel power gain $g[i]$ remains constant during the transmission of a given packet i but varies over time because of multipath fading and/or shadowing. The received signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the receiver follows an exponential distribution of mean $\bar{\gamma}$, leading to a probability of outage P_{out} when the SNR falls below a certain threshold. The number of transmissions for successfully sending a packet N is geometrically distributed. The throughput for a bandwidth B is obtained as:

$$R = (1 - P_{out}) \log_2 \left(\bar{\gamma} \log \left(\frac{1}{1 - P_{out}} \right) \right)$$

And the energy consumed by a UE to transmit a packet is

$$E_{UE}^{trx} = \frac{1}{1 - P_{out}} \frac{\sigma P_{trx}}{R}$$

Additionally, the queuing model follows a G/G/1 system, where images arrive at a rate and experience a service time distribution that are both generic. The upper bound of the waiting time in the queue depends on the coefficient of variation of the arrival and service processes, the mean service time, and the system utilization. For the service distribution, it is easy to compute these statistics based on the outage and rates calculated before. For the traffic distribution, the closed-form expression is not tractable and the coefficient of variation is empirically computed.

The system model is completed with a DRX procedure to reduce the power consumption by the UE, following the parameters defined in cellular technologies [LLH+23]. The main principle is that the UE monitors the control channel during a predefined-ON period and enters into an energy-saving state turning off its RF chain (OFF period) if there is no uplink or downlink packet.

Proposed methodology and solution

Following a SemCom and GO-based approach, the focus is on transmitting only the data necessary for the receiver to achieve its goal, rather than preserving all information, which includes selecting the optimal coding strategy based on network conditions.

Traditional source coding techniques (lossy and lossless) are the baseline for data compression. Lossless encoding (LL) ensures that all data can be reconstructed at the receiver, while lossy coding sacrifices non-critical details for higher compression. The first enhancement considered in the solution is the use of lossless coding (LL).

Second, we also consider the use of GO source encoding, specifically semantic segmentation techniques, to extract and transmit only the most relevant aspects of an image. Instead of transmitting full-resolution images, the system sends compact representations of scene semantics, such as identified road hazards, traffic signals, and vehicle positions. Specifically, RealtimeSeg, a lightweight and efficient semantic segmentation algorithm, is applied to extract meaningful image content while minimizing computational overhead. The goodness of the segmentation algorithms is measured in terms of energy consumption to complete a given task.

Third, Bloom Filters can be used to eliminate redundant or low-priority messages before transmission. They operate with predefined filtering rules, which are dynamically updated using ML/DL techniques. This ensures that critical messages are never dropped (zero false negatives), though some irrelevant messages may occasionally pass through (false positives), while reducing the bandwidth consumption. The Bloom Filters are characterized by the Bloom filtering factor (BFF) defined as

$$BFF = 1 - \frac{E[\hat{\sigma}]}{E[\sigma]}$$

where $E[\hat{\sigma}]$ is the average length of packets after being filtered. The obtained BFF after filtering will highly depend on the degree of redundancy of data traffic.

These three elements when integrated into the system model described before provide a complete framework that is then evaluated to demonstrate the gains of the SemCom approach. Specifically, the performance evaluation considers the application of some of the enhancements and the combination of all of them: LL, Bloom filtering, and GO source encoding (segmentation).

Finally, the proposed SemCom framework is integrated into existing ITS architectures ensuring compatibility with standardized networking protocols. Specifically, it is proposed that all the AI and ML/DL techniques operate within the application layer, just below the final applications.

Results

The evaluation demonstrates that SemCom drastically reduces the required bandwidth while improving key performance indicators such as latency and network load capacity.

Figure 4-12 shows cumulative the different components that made up the joint result of using filtering and GO source coding, as a function of the system load ρ . As we can see, in terms of delay, the main component is due to the data transmission (including DRX, queueing, and the transmission), but in terms of energy consumption is more evenly distributed specially for GO source coding and transmission.

Figure 4-12. (a) Average message delay (b) Total energy consumption

Figure 4-13 shows the maximum supported load to obtain a packet delay below 20 ms. In all cases, the supported load increases when using source coding with respect to the baseline setting (marked as a dashed line). However, the improvement when using Bloom Filters and GO source encoding are very noticeable. For example, when we use a Bloom Filter that gets a BFF = 0.4, we can increase the supported load up to ~84%. When using GO encoding, we have measured that this value is increased up to ~588% for a summarization capacity of 0.8 (the latter defined as one minus the ratio of information extracted by the GO encoder as compared to raw data). Finally, the figure also includes the maximum supported load when we use several source coding techniques at a time. With the joint use of all the source coding techniques, we have obtained improvements in the maximum supported load of ~820%. These performance gains are conditional on fulfilling the task-specific requirements related to inferences on the transmitted images, and a future work could focus on these aspects. In our evaluations, this part is addressed through the selected value of summarization capacity.

Figure 4-13. Latency and energy performance versus CPU operating frequency

Conclusions

SemCom emerges as a critical paradigm for enabling the efficient operation and meeting the stringent demands of future ITS and V2X networks. This involves intelligent, application-aware data processing at the source, a crucial element for the successful deployment of advanced V2X services with limited wireless resources. Traditional lossless source coding is generally

detrimental in this context due to high energy demands. Instead, the combination of Bloom filtering and goal-oriented source coding have proved to be key enablers for achieving both low delays and energy-efficient ITS, together with semantic segmentation for image transmission. While energy efficiency gains with SemCom depend on the computational complexity of the algorithms, techniques like RealtimeSeg demonstrate the potential for simultaneous improvements in latency, supported load, and energy consumption.

5 Conclusions

A critical requirement of the scenarios considered in 6G-GOALS is time. Meeting end-to-end performance and accuracy targets is not just about what is transmitted, but also when and how. In this task, the project has explored different enhancements in goal-oriented and semantic communications that are sensitive to time:

- Novel frameworks and methodologies have been presented for improving communication efficiency under timing constraints, in diverse scenarios like IoT, V2X, and digital twins.
- A key focus is on enabling intelligent data transmission by considering the meaning and relevance of information, utilizing diverse AI techniques that include foundation models, and dynamic resource allocation to optimize metrics such as latency, energy consumption, and accuracy.
- Ultimately, these set of initial results contribute to a unified vision of the role of time in the design and performance of SemCom and GO communications.

The second half of the project will build upon these initial theoretical frameworks and algorithmic solutions, and further connect them to the broader 6G-GOALS vision of a semantic and goal-oriented architecture and protocol definition, in which time and tightly integrated control-computation-communication-inference loops play a central role.

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